

Heat Exchanger Physics

PROBLEM: How to find the hot & cold side exit temperatures given their input states & the exchanger UA? Works for counter and co-flow. Model developed for counter flow as the maths is more general.

Consider the counter flow heat exchanger in Figure 1.1

Figure 1.1 Counter flow heat exchanger

Applying energy balances on the hot and cold fluid elements bounded by dx with both fluid temperatures decreasing in the positive x direction.

$$dq = -m_a c_a d\theta = -m_b c_b dt$$

$\therefore$

$$d\theta = -\frac{dq}{m_a c_a}, dt = -\frac{dq}{m_b c_b} \quad (1)$$

$\therefore$

$$d\theta - dt = -dq \left(\frac{1}{m_a c_a} - \frac{1}{m_b c_b} \right) \rightarrow d(\theta - t) = -dq \left(\frac{1}{m_a c_a} - \frac{1}{m_b c_b} \right)$$

Also

$$dq = U\sigma(\theta - t)dx \rightarrow d(\theta - t) = -U\sigma(\theta - t)dx \left(\frac{1}{m_a c_a} - \frac{1}{m_b c_b} \right)$$

$\therefore$

$$\frac{d(\theta - t)}{(\theta - t)} = -U\sigma \left(\frac{1}{m_a c_a} - \frac{1}{m_b c_b} \right) dx$$

∴

$$\int_{z_1}^{z_2} \frac{dz}{z} = -U\sigma \left(\frac{1}{m_a c_a} - \frac{1}{m_b c_b} \right) \int_0^L dx$$

$$\ln \left(\frac{z_2}{z_1} \right) = -U\sigma \left(\frac{1}{m_a c_a} - \frac{1}{m_b c_b} \right) L = -UA \left(\frac{1}{m_a c_a} - \frac{1}{m_b c_b} \right)$$

∴

$$\frac{(\theta_2 - t_2)}{(\theta_1 - t_1)} = \exp(-k) = \alpha \quad (2)$$

∴

$$\theta_2 - t_2 = \alpha(\theta_1 - t_1)$$

∴

$$\theta_2 = t_2 + \alpha(\theta_1 - t_1) \quad (3)$$

So that

$$\theta_2 - \theta_1 = (t_2 - \theta_1) + \alpha(\theta_1 - t_1) \quad (4)$$

Across the exchanger an energy balance on the two fluids gives:

$$m_b c_b (t_1 - t_2) = m_a c_a (\theta_1 - \theta_2) \rightarrow t_1 - t_2 = \beta(\theta_1 - \theta_2)$$

∴

$$t_1 = t_2 - \beta(\theta_2 - \theta_1) \quad (5)$$

Substitute (5) into (4)

$$\theta_2 - \theta_1 = (t_2 - \theta_1) + \alpha(\theta_1 - (t_2 - \beta(\theta_2 - \theta_1)))$$

∴

$$\theta_2 - \theta_1 = t_2 - \theta_1 + \alpha\theta_1 - \alpha t_2 + \alpha\beta(\theta_2 - \theta_1)$$

$$(\theta_2 - \theta_1)(1 - \alpha\beta) = t_2(1 - \alpha) - \theta_1(1 - \alpha)$$

$$(\theta_2 - \theta_1) = \frac{(1 - \alpha)(t_2 - \theta_1)}{(1 - \alpha\beta)} \quad (6)$$

This allows a definition of the exchanger efficiency e such that

$$(\theta_2 - \theta_1) = e(t_2 - \theta_1) \quad (7)$$

$$(t_1 - t_2) = \beta(\theta_1 - \theta_2) \quad (8)$$

Substituting (7) into (8)

$$t_1 = t_2 + \beta(\theta_1 - \theta_1 - e(t_2 - \theta_1))$$

$\therefore$

$$t_1 = t_2 + \beta(e(\theta_1 - t_2))$$

$\therefore$

$$t_1 = t_2 + e\beta(\theta_1 - t_2) \tag{11}$$

where

$$\alpha = \exp\left(-UA\left(\frac{1}{m_a c_a} - \frac{1}{m_b c_b}\right)\right)$$

$$\beta = \frac{m_a c_a}{m_b c_b} \tag{12}$$

$$e = \frac{1 - \alpha}{1 - \alpha\beta}$$

Model in a box.

$$\theta_2 = \theta_1 + e(t_2 - \theta_1)$$

$$t_1 = t_2 + e\beta(\theta_1 - t_2)$$

$$\alpha = \exp\left(-UA\left(\frac{1}{m_a c_a} - \frac{1}{m_b c_b}\right)\right)$$

$$\beta = \frac{m_a c_a}{m_b c_b}$$

$$e = \frac{1 - \alpha}{1 - \alpha\beta}$$

